

Thiosulphato-Cobalt Complexes and Complex Cobalt Thiosulphates. Part I.

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In spite of a voluminous work done on the double and complex thiosulphates of various metallic elements, very little attempt has been made to prepare cobalti-ammine compounds with the thiosulphate radicle either inside or outside the complex zone. One chloro-pentammine-cobaltic thiosulphate has been described by Jørgensen (*J. pr. Chem.*, 878, [2] 18, 212). In this the thiosulphate group occurs outside the co-ordination sphere. Following Werner's method (*Annalen*, 1911, 386, 81) for sulphito-chloride, Duff (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 450) investigated the reaction between sodium thiosulphate and *trans*-dichloro-diethylenediamine-cobaltic chloride. On evaporating the mixed solution the complex was found to decompose with the separation of cobalt sulphide. However, he (*loc. cit.*) succeeded in preparing a thiosulphato-bromide by the interaction of carbonato-diethylene-diamine-cobaltic bromide with barium thiosulphate in a hot solution. This is the only complex cobalt compound described in literature with a thiosulphate group in the complex. The thiosulphate radicle occupies here two co-ordination positions in the complex and one of its sulphur atoms is directly linked to the central cobalt atom giving rise to the brown colour of the diethylenediaminethiosulphato-cobaltic bromide. That a sulphur atom directly linked to the central metallic atom in the complex causes the brown colour of the complex sulphito- and thiosulphato-cobalt salts has been definitely established by Werner and by Duff (*loc. cit.*). In the present paper, the preparation and properties of a number of entirely new complex thiosulphato-cobalti-ammine and cobalti-ammine thiosulphates have been described. The methods of their preparation completely differ from that adopted by Duff in the preparation of the above-mentioned thiosulphato-bromide and different methods had to be devised for different compounds.

In all cases the starting material was either cobalt hydroxide, cobalt chloride or cobalt nitrate. By the action of ammonium or sodium thiosulphate and ammonia in varying strength upon the above-mentioned cobalt compounds in a current of air, the following thiosulphato-cobalti-ammine complexes and cobalti-ammine thiosulphates have been obtained.

The compounds I, VI and VII are all red or purple-red showing that the thiosulphate radicle is linked to the central cobalt atom directly through an oxygen atom as indicated below :—

where X is either a mono-valent or a bi-valent radicle.

Compounds III and IV are yellow and hence contain a directly linked sulphur atom in the complex grouping as detailed below :—

All the complex thiosulphato-compounds mentioned above belong to the monoacido-pentammine series and the thiosulphate radicle

occupies only one co-ordination position in the complex. They all form well-defined crystals and are quite stable, though in solution they hydrolyse very slowly into aquo-salts as is usually the case with mono-acido-pentammine salts in which a bivalent acid radicle occupies only one co-ordination position.

The case of sulphito-pentammine thiosulphate (III) is of special interest as it is formed from the mother-liquor after the separation of the thiosulphato-pentammine thiosulphate. Evidently a sulphite is formed in solution from the thiosulphate during oxidation or afterwards. This is discussed in detail in the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiosulphato-pentammine Cobaltic Thiosulphate (I).

Cobalt hydroxide prepared from 20 g. of cobalt chloride and washed free from alkali and chlorides was mixed up with 25 g. of ammonium thiosulphate dissolved in 25 c.c. of water. The mixture was then treated with 150 c.c. of concentrated ammonia (d 0.90 = 25%) and thoroughly stirred. The solution was then filtered from the undissolved residue and a brisk current of air was passed through it for 3-4 hours till practically all the black crystals of oxy-cobalt compound separated in the beginning redissolved. Sometimes some purple-red crystals of the thiosulphato-pentammine separated before the disappearance of all oxy-cobalt salts. The solution was next filtered and allowed to stand overnight in a closed vessel. A thick crust of dark purple-red crystals was found at the bottom of the flask next morning. The crystals were then filtered and the filtrate was reserved. They were first washed with dilute ammonia, then with alcohol and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. Yield, 5-6 gms. (Found: Co, 18.58, 18.5, 18.45; S, 29.5; NH_3 , 26.4, 26.58. $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5]_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 18.38; S, 29.9, NH_3 , 26.4 per cent.).

The substance thus obtained is quite pure and can be recrystallized from aqueous ammonia. It is very sparingly soluble in water and is decomposed by mineral acids and acetic acid with liberation of sulphur dioxide and sulphur. The solution of the substance is alkaline to litmus. Silver nitrate at once gives a brownish black precipitate of silver sulphide in the cold, and the filtrate, on treating with acetic acid and warming, gives a further precipitate of silver sulphide or the filtrate after the removal of silver with ammonium

chloride, liberates sulphur dioxide and precipitates sulphur on boiling with dilute sulphuric acid. This indicates the presence of the thiosulphate both outside and inside the complex. On shaking with silver oxide however, the whole of the thiosulphate both from inside and outside the complex is removed and the alkaline solution, on heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid, gives chloropentamine chloride. This proves that the substance contains a pentamine complex. Lead acetate solution behaves like silver nitrate. Absence of sulphite and thionate was established by qualitative tests. On treating the substance with concentrated nitric acid or bromine a rose-coloured precipitate of sulphato-pentamine sulphate is obtained. The substance dissolves in dilute caustic soda solution (10 per cent.) evidently as a hydroxo-salt from which it can be precipitated unchanged by alcohol.

A better yield of the compound was obtained when instead of 150 c.c. of 25 per cent. ammonia, 250 c.c. of 12.5 per cent. ammonia was used. Thiosulphato-pentamine thiosulphate was also obtained by passing a current of air through a solution made from cobalt chloride (10 g.), ammonium thiosulphate (15 g.) and concentrated ammonia (50 c.c.). The method of procedure is exactly the same as described above, but the yield is smaller.

Tri-ethylenediamine Cobaltic Thiosulphate (II).

When the thiosulphato-pentamine thiosulphate was treated on the water bath at 60° for sometime with an excess of 10 per cent. ethylenediamine solution it was converted into a yellow, easily soluble crystalline compound. It was washed with a little water then with alcohol and finally dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. (Found: Co, 14.1; S, 23.08; N, 20.4. $[\text{Co}(\text{En})_3](\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)$, requires Co, 14.1; S, 23.07; N, 20.2 per cent.).

Sulphito-pentamine Thiosulphate (III).

The filtrate obtained after the separation of the compound (I) was again transferred into a flask and a current of air was passed through it for several hours until the strong smell of ammonia nearly disappeared. The solution became brown and was then allowed to stand for some days being occasionally filtered from the precipitated sulphur or a little thiosulphato-pentamine salt. After a time yellowish brown crystals separated from the solution. These

were then filtered, washed with water, then with alcohol and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. The substance can be recrystallized from 5 per cent. ammonia solution. (Found: Co, 20·98, 21·0; S, 23·1, 22·95; NH₃, 30·3. [(NH₃)₅Co(SO₃)₂]₂S₂O₈ requires Co, 21·07; S, 22·86; NH₃, 30·3 per cent.)

A hydrated variety of sulphito-pentammine thiosulphate was obtained from the filtrate from thiosulphato-pentammine thiosulphate when after passing a current of air through the filtrate as before, the latter was treated again with concentrated ammonia liquor. A silky yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained. The crystals were washed as usual and dried in air. (Found: Co, 20·1; NH₃, 29·27. [(NH₃)₅Co(SO₃)₂]₂S₂O₈·1½H₂O requires Co, 20·1; NH₃, 29·0 per cent.)

The same substance was also obtained when a solution of carbonato-tetrammine cobaltic nitrate was mixed with an ammoniacal ammonium thiosulphate solution and the mixture was allowed to stand in a closed bottle for about a week. The yellowish brown crystals separated at the bottom of the bottle were then filtered, washed, and recrystallized from 5 per cent. ammonia solution. They were then dried as usual. On qualitative and quantitative analysis they were found to be sulphito-pentammine thiosulphate admixed with slight impurities which could not be removed by recrystallization.

The formation of sulphito-thiosulphate in all these cases presents an interesting phenomenon, where the sulphito-salt was formed in a solution to which no sulphite was previously added. It is evidently formed from the slow decomposition of ammonium thiosulphate with separation of sulphur.

In the first two cases some ammonium sulphite might have also been formed during the oxidation of cobalt by air according to the equation:

cobalt salts probably acting as a catalyst. In the last case the ammonium sulphite and thiosulphate then probably react with carbonato-tetrammine cobaltic nitrate, [(NH₃)₄·Co·CO₃]NO, giving sulphito-tetrammine cobaltic thiosulphate, [(NH₃)₄·Co·SO₃]₂S₂O₈, which in presence of ammonia leads to the formation of the

pentammine sulphito-thiosulphate. This is supported by the fact already stated that the pentammine sulphito-thiosulphate can also be obtained by the addition of strong ammonia to the filtrate from thiosulphato-thiosulphate, which has become too poor in ammonia and does not separate the sulphito-pentammine salt by itself.

The sulphito-thiosulphate is alkaline to litmus, more or less sparingly soluble in water, dissolves in cold caustic alkali to an orange brown solution. A solution of the salt with silver nitrate solution gives a brownish black precipitate of silver sulphide in the cold; the filtrate on boiling with acetic acid or dilute sulphuric acid liberates sulphur dioxide without any separation of silver sulphide, but grey metallic silver is only precipitated. Lead acetate solution behaves in a similar fashion. Absence of thionates and sulphates and the presence of sulphites and thiosulphates were also definitely proved by qualitative tests after removing the cobalt as sulphide with sulphuretted hydrogen from an ammoniacal solution of the salt and then removing the excess of sulphuretted hydrogen by cadmium carbonate. When shaken vigorously with silver oxide, a strongly alkaline brown solution was obtained, which after filtration and evaporation with concentrated hydrochloric acid, gave characteristic crystals of chloropentammine chloride.

Hydroxo-tetrammine Cobaltic Sulphite (IV).

The sulphito-pentammine thiosulphate was dissolved in 5 per cent. caustic soda solution to a clear orange-coloured liquid which on treatment with alcohol gave a precipitate of copper-coloured beautiful silky plates. These were first washed with 30 per cent. alcohol and then with absolute alcohol. The crystals were then dried in vacuo over calcium chloride. (Found: Co, 22.6; S, 12.0; NH₃, 26.0. [(NH₃)₄·Co(OH)SO₃] 2H₂O requires Co, 22.7; S, 12.3; NH₃, 26.1 per cent.).

The substance is readily soluble in water and is strongly alkaline to litmus and precipitates silver oxide from a solution of silver nitrate. It does not react with potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide and potassium chromate solution. With barium chloride solution a white turbidity appears which gradually increases on keeping and after sometime a black precipitate of cobaltic oxide is formed. All these properties indicate that the substance is a hydroxo-compound. It readily absorbs carbon dioxide and forms a carbonate.

A compound of the composition $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{SO}_3\cdot\text{OH}, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been described by Hofmann and Reinsch (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, **16**, 384). They prepared it by the action of silver oxide upon a solution of sulphito-aquo-tetrammine cobaltic thiocyanate and represented it as sulphito-aquo-tetrammine cobaltic hydroxide $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{H}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{SO}_3]\text{OH}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. But it is very unlikely that an aquo-salt can be formed in the present case from a strongly alkaline solution. Of course in aqueous solution all hydroxo-compounds are hydrolysed into aquo-hydroxides and behave as such. The compound could also be represented as $[(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Co}(\text{SO}_3)]\text{OH}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; but its method of formation from a pentammine salt with evolution of one molecule of ammonia as well as the usually greater tendency of the sulphito group to occupy only one co-ordination position in the complex (the number of sulphito-compounds in which the sulphito-group occupies one co-ordination position is much larger than those in which it occupies two) strongly suggest the constitution (IV) given above. The reaction leading to its formation can be represented as below:—

Hexammine Cobaltic Chloro-thiosulphate (V).

Crystallized cobalt chloride (10 g.), ammonium chloride (10 g.) and sodium thiosulphate (24 g.) were dissolved in water (50 c.c.) and treated with ammonia (120 c.c., *d* 0.90). The solution was filtered and a brisk current of air was passed through it for a few minutes. Yellow crystals began to separate at once but the mixture was allowed to stand over-night. Next morning the crystals were separated by filtration from the mother-liquor and purified by recrystallization from 4 per cent. ammonia solution. The crystals were first washed with 20 per cent. alcohol containing a little ammonia and then with absolute alcohol. They were dried in vacuo over calcium chloride. Yield 8 g. approximately. In serves as an excellent method for preparing hexammine salts. (Found: Co, 18.52; S, 20.65; Cl, 11.1; NH_3 , 32.7. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{ClS}_2\text{O}_3$ requires Co, 19.1; S, 20.71; Cl, 11.8; NH_3 , 38.0 per cent.).

The substance forms beautiful silky yellow crystals, fairly soluble in water. The solution can be boiled without decomposition. It

gives all the characteristic reactions for hexammine salts. The whole of the thiosulphate and chlorine are precipitated by silver nitrate solution in the cold.

Thiosulphato-pentammine Cobaltic Chloride (VI).

Hydrated cobalt chloride (10 g.) dissolved in the least quantity of cold water was mixed with ammonium chloride (24 g.) and sodium thiosulphate (12 g.). To the solution 60 c.c. of 7 per cent. ammonia were added. The solution was filtered and a rapid current of air was passed through the filtrate for an hour and a half, the solution being cooled in ice water all the while. Purple-red crystals separated in large quantities. The mixture was allowed to stand for about two hours in the cold. The crystals were then filtered and washed with 2 per cent. ammonia solution. The crystals thus obtained were contaminated with some thiosulphato-pentammine thiosulphate, which could not be removed by simple recrystallization. They were therefore dissolved in the least amount of water and then salted out by the addition of a saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The crystals were separated, washed first with ammoniacal water and then with alcohol. They were dried as usual in vacuo over sulphuric acid. (Found: Co, 20·8; S, 22·15; Cl, 12·25; NH₃, 29·16. [S₂O₃Co(NH₃)₅] Cl requires Co, 20·24; S, 21·96; Cl, 12·18; NH₃, 29·16 per cent.).

The substance thus prepared has a dark red colour and is fairly soluble in water. Silver nitrate solution gives a precipitate of silver chloride from its solution in the cold; the filtrate on boiling with dilute sulphuric acid gives a black precipitate of silver sulphide. These reactions prove that the chlorine is in the outer zone and the thiosulphate group is in the inner zone of the complex. With concentrated hydrochloric acid in the cold it is transformed into chloropentammine cobaltic chloride.

Thiosulphato-pentammine Bromide.

To a cold strong solution of the above thiosulphato-chloride, a saturated solution of sodium bromide was added. Dark red crystals of the bromide separated out. These were washed and dried as in the case of the chloride. (Found: Co, 17·84; Br, 24·1. [S₂O₃·Co(NH₃)₅] Br requires Co, 17·6; Br, 23·8 per cent.).

The aqueous solution in the cold gives a precipitate of silver bromide with silver nitrate solution. The filtrate on boiling with dilute sulphuric acid gives a black precipitate of silver sulphide.

Thiosulphato-pentammine Iodide.

To a cold strong solution of the chloride, crystals of potassium iodide were added. The dark red crystalline precipitate thus obtained was washed and dried as usual. (Found: Co, 15·54; I, 33·67. $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5]$ I requires Co, 15·4; I, 33·2 per cent.).

An aqueous solution of the substance in the cold gives a yellowish precipitate of silver iodide with silver nitrate solution. In the filtrate the thiosulphate can be detected as above.

Reactions of the Thiosulphato-pentammine Cobaltic Ion.

A solution of the thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic chloride gives a red precipitate with potassium ferrocyanide solution and a chocolate-brown precipitate with the ferricyanide solution. With potassium stanni-chloride it forms red crystals of the thiosulphato-pentammine stanni-chloride which is readily hydrolysed by water. With sodium platinichloride it gives an insoluble brown platinichloride. With mercuric chloride solution a voluminous light-rose-coloured precipitate is obtained.

Thiosulphato-pentammine Cobaltic Nitrate (VI).

Crystalline cobalt nitrate (12 g.), ammonium nitrate (15 g.) and sodium thiosulphate (24 g.) were dissolved in water (50 c.c.) and treated with strong ammonia (120 c.c., *d* 0·90). The solution, after filtration, was treated with a rapid stream of air for about two hours and it was filtered from any black oxycobalt salts. Air was again passed through the filtrate for about an hour till dull purple-red crystals began to separate. The mixture was then allowed to stand overnight in the cold. Next morning the crystals were collected, washed with cold ammoniacal water and recrystallized from hot 4 per cent. ammonia solution. The substance was again washed with aqueous alcohol containing a little ammonia, then with alcohol and afterwards dried in vacuo over calcium chloride. (Found: Co, 18·5, 18·7; S, 20·5; N, 26·77, NH_3 , 26·73. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_3]$ NO_3 requires Co, 18·55; S, 20·12; N, 26·4; NH_3 , 26·7 per cent.).

The substance is sparingly soluble in water; it gives no precipitate with silver nitrate solution in the cold but on keeping for sometime the solution gradually turns turbid and finally a black precipitate of silver sulphide appears. On treatment with silver oxide the whole

of the thiosulphate is removed; the filtrate, after the removal of the excess of silver with hydrochloric acid and on evaporation with strong hydrochloric acid, gives characteristic crystals of chloropentammine chloride. The presence of nitrate group was established by qualitative tests. That the substance is a thiosulphato-pentammine cobaltic nitrate is further confirmed by converting it into a dithionate as described below.

Thiosulphato-pentammine Cobaltic Dithionate (VII).

To a strong solution of the thiosulphato-nitrate in 4 per cent. aqueous ammonia, a concentrated solution of sodium dithionate was added. On cooling well-defined purple-red crystals separated out. These were washed with water and then with alcohol and dried as usual in vacuo over sulphuric acid. (Found: Co, 17.69; S, 28.85; NH_3 , 25.27; N, 21.5. $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co.S}_2\text{O}_8]$, S_2O_8 requires Co, 17.55; S, 28.57; NH_3 , 25.8; N, 20.83 per cent.).

The substance is sparingly soluble in water. Silver nitrate solution gives no immediate precipitate in the cold but, on keeping, the solution becomes turbid and finally a black precipitate of silver sulphide appears; but the precipitation does not become complete even after an hour.

Thiosulphato pentammine Chromate (VII).

To a concentrated solution of the thiosulphato-pentammine chloride in the cold a saturated solution of potassium chromate was added. Brilliant silky leaflets separated after a time. These were washed with dilute ammonia and recrystallized from hot dilute ammonia (2 per cent.). The product was washed and dried as usual. (Found: Co, 18.6; Cr, 8.44. $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoS}_2\text{O}_8]$, CrO_4 requires Co, 18.8; Cr, 8.28 per cent.).

It forms red silky crystals, very sparingly soluble in water. An aqueous solution in the cold gives a red precipitate of silver chromate with silver nitrate solution. The filtrate from silver chromate gives all characteristic reactions for thiosulphuric acid.

Nitropentammine Thiosulphate (VII).

Cobalt hydroxide from 10 g. of cobalt chloride crystals was mixed up with ammonium thiosulphate (20 g.) and sodim nitrite (14 g.)

dissolved in a small quantity of water. The mixture was then poured down into 90 c.c. of 25 per cent. ammonia and a rapid current of air was passed through the mixture for about 3 hours. It was then filtered and the filtrate was allowed to stand overnight. A large crop of brownish yellow crystals was found at the bottom of the vessel next morning. These were filtered, washed and recrystallized from dilute ammonia. The product thus obtained is bright yellow in colour. (Found: Co, 19.74; S, 21.05, 21.55; N, 28.5; NH_3 , 28.3. [$(\text{NH}_3)_2$ Co. NO_2] S_2O_3 requires Co, 19.5; S, 21.2; N, 27.81; NH_3 , 28.14 per cent.).

It is sparingly soluble in water. The solution gives immediately a black precipitate of silver sulphide with silver nitrate solution. The filtrate on treatment with sulphuric acid and warming gives out nitrous fumes.

Method of Analysis.

In the above compounds cobalt was always estimated, except in the case of the thiosulphato-chromate, as cobalt sulphate by evaporating with sulphuric acid. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate by oxidizing the sulphites, thiosulphates or dithionates with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide. Chromium in the case of the thiosulphato-chromate was estimated volumetrically after igniting the compound and then fusing it with sodium peroxide. Ammonia was estimated by distillation. In some cases total nitrogen was estimated by combustion. The halogen elements were estimated as their silver salts as usual after oxidizing the compounds with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide to convert the thiosulphates into sulphates. Cobalt in the thiosulphato-chromate was estimated by precipitating as cobalt rubeanate after removing the chromium as chromate by boiling with caustic soda and then dissolving the cobaltic oxide with hydrochloric acid. The solution of the cobalt chloride thus obtained was then neutralized with ammonia, treated with sodium acetate and an alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid was added in excess to precipitate the cobalt. The cobalt rubeanate was finally converted into cobalt sulphate by treatment with a mixture of nitric acid and sulphuric acid and weighed as such. (Ray and Ray, *This Journal*, 1926, 3, 124).